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Solar Powered Portable Heating and Cooling Bag Based on Peltier Technology

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Abstract: Maintaining the required temperature of food, beverages, medicines, and other temperature-sensitive items during transportation is a significant challenge, particularly in the absence of portable temperature control systems. Conventional insulated bags are unable to actively regulate temperature, resulting in spoilage of perishable goods and reduced effectiveness of medical supplies. This paper presents the design and implementation of a solar-powered portable dual-temperature box based on thermoelectric (Peltier) technology. The proposed system employs a Peltier module to provide both heating and cooling by reversing the polarity through a Double Pole Double Throw (DPDT) switch. An Arduino Uno continuously monitors the internal temperature using a thermistor sensor, and the measured temperature is displayed in real time on the serial monitor. The system is powered by a rechargeable lithium-ion battery pack, which can be charged using a 100 W solar panel through a charge controller, enabling portable and sustainable operation. Experimental evaluation demonstrated that the prototype reduced the internal temperature from 28°C to 19.6°C in cooling mode and increased it from 28°C to 47°C in heating mode within 30 minutes, confirming the effectiveness of the proposed design. The developed prototype offers a compact, low-cost, energy-efficient, and environmentally friendly solution for portable temperature-controlled storage with potential applications in food transportation, healthcare, and outdoor activities.

Keywords: Arduino Uno, Lithium-Ion Battery, Peltier Module, Portable Temperature Control, Renewable Energy, Solar-Powered System, Thermoelectric Technology, Thermistor.

1. INTRODUCTION

When we travel, we often carry items like food, drinks, or medicines that need to stay at a proper temperature. If these items become too hot or too cold, food can spoil, drinks may lose their taste, and medicines might not work properly. Normal bags cannot solve this problem because they do not have any temperature control. To solve this issue, this paper introduces a dual-temperature bag that can both heat and cool items as needed. The bag uses a Peltier chip, which is a small device that produces cooling on one side and heating on the other when electricity is applied. This chip is controlled by an Arduino, which works as the brain of the system. The Arduino continuously checks the temperature inside the bag and keeps it within safe limits. A metal box is placed inside the bag to hold the items, and it helps spread the heat or cold evenly so everything stays at the right temperature.

The bag is powered by a rechargeable battery, making it easy to carry while traveling. To make the system eco-friendly, the battery can also be charged using a solar panel through a charge controller. A DPDT switch is provided so the user can easily change between heating and cooling modes. An LCD display shows the current temperature inside the bag in real time. For safety, a relay module automatically turns off the power to the Peltier chip if the temperature goes beyond safe limits, preventing overheating and protecting the items inside.

This product is designed to be simple, low-cost, and practical. It is very useful for travellers who want to keep food fresh during long journeys, students who carry meals to college, and patients who need to store medicines safely. By using smart electronics and solar energy, the dual-temperature bag provides a modern and eco- friendly solution to a common daily problem .Here Figure 1 represents the hardware connections and Figure 2 is the design of the Solar peltier portable bag.

Figure 1: Hardware Connection – Front View

Figure 2: Design of Solar peltier portable bag

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Maintaining the required temperature of food, beverages, medicines, and other perishable products during transportation has become increasingly important in healthcare, domestic, and commercial applications. Conventional storage containers are unable to actively regulate temperature, resulting in food spoilage and reduced effectiveness of temperature-sensitive medical supplies. Thermoelectric cooling technology based on the Peltier effect has emerged as a promising solution because of its compact size, low maintenance, environmentally friendly operation, and ability to provide both heating and cooling without refrigerants. Researchers have explored various approaches to improve the performance, efficiency, and portability of thermoelectric systems.

D. Zhao and G. Tan [1] presented a comprehensive review of thermoelectric cooling technologies, discussing the operating principles, material properties, and practical applications of thermoelectric devices. Their study highlighted the advantages of Peltier modules, including compact design, silent operation, and environmental friendliness, while also identifying relatively low energy efficiency as one of the major challenges limiting their widespread adoption.

Sarbu and Dorca [2] reviewed solar-powered thermoelectric cooling systems and emphasized the potential of integrating photovoltaic energy with thermoelectric modules for sustainable cooling applications. The authors concluded that solar-powered thermoelectric systems can significantly reduce dependence on conventional energy sources, although improvements in system efficiency and thermal management are still required.

Kherkhar et al. [3] investigated the thermal performance of an Arduino-based thermoelectric cooling system using a PID control algorithm. Their work demonstrated that automatic temperature regulation improves temperature stability and enhances cooling performance. However, the inclusion of advanced control techniques increases system complexity and implementation cost.

Syednezhad and Najafi [4] conducted a parametric analysis of a solar-powered thermoelectric heating and cooling system for building applications. The study showed that integrating solar energy with thermoelectric modules can provide an environmentally friendly heating and cooling solution while reducing dependence on conventional electricity. The authors also emphasized that system performance strongly depends on operating conditions and proper thermal design.

Kaiprath and K. K. V. V. [5] reviewed recent developments in photovoltaic-powered thermoelectric cooling systems and discussed various techniques for improving system performance, including heat sink optimization, enhanced heat transfer, and advanced control strategies. Their findings indicate that combining renewable energy with thermoelectric technology can improve system sustainability and energy utilization.

Khan et al. [6] designed and experimentally evaluated a portable thermoelectric vaccine carrier box using Peltier modules. The proposed system successfully maintained the required storage temperature for medical applications, demonstrating the feasibility of thermoelectric cooling in portable healthcare devices. However, continuous operation required an external power source, limiting long-duration portability.

Shree et al. [7] developed a low-cost Arduino-based thermoelectric refrigerator that demonstrated the practical implementation of Peltier cooling using readily available electronic components. Their system provided satisfactory cooling performance for small-scale applications while maintaining a simple and economical design.

Senthil Kumar et al. [8] experimentally investigated the effect of thermoelectric cooling on photovoltaic solar panels. Their results showed that reducing the operating temperature of solar panels improves electrical efficiency and overall power generation, demonstrating the complementary relationship between solar energy and thermoelectric technology.

Riffat and Ma [9] reviewed different methods for improving the coefficient of performance (COP) of thermoelectric cooling systems. Their study discussed the influence of heat sink design, thermoelectric materials, and operating conditions on system efficiency, highlighting the importance of effective thermal management for practical applications.

Giaretto and Campagnoli [10] experimentally analyzed the Thomson effect in commercial thermoelectric modules over a wide operating temperature range. Their investigation improved the understanding of heat transfer mechanisms inside thermoelectric devices and provided valuable insights for enhancing module performance.

Rowe [11] discussed thermoelectric technology as a renewable energy solution through waste heat recovery and highlighted its potential for improving overall energy efficiency in various engineering applications. In another study, Rowe [12] emphasized that thermoelectric devices offer an environmentally friendly alternative for electrical power generation because they operate without moving parts or harmful refrigerants.

Goldsmid [13] presented the fundamental principles of thermoelectricity, including the Seebeck, Peltier, and Thomson effects, together with the characteristics of thermoelectric materials and device operation. Snyder and Toberer [14] further explained the relationship between material properties and thermoelectric performance, emphasizing that improving the figure of merit (ZT) is essential for developing highly efficient thermoelectric systems. Similarly, DiSalvo [15] discussed the applications of thermoelectric technology in both cooling and power generation, highlighting its potential in portable and energy-efficient devices.

Overall, the reviewed literature demonstrates that thermoelectric technology has significant potential for portable heating and cooling applications because of its compact size, reliability, and environmental benefits. Although previous studies have focused on improving thermoelectric efficiency, renewable energy integration, and automatic temperature control, limited attention has been given to developing a simple, low-cost, portable dual-temperature bag capable of both heating and cooling for everyday transportation of food, beverages, and medicines. The proposed work addresses this need by integrating a Peltier module, solar-powered rechargeable battery, manual DPDT mode selection, and real-time LCD temperature monitoring into a compact and practical portable system.

3. BLOCK DIAGRAM AND DESCRIPTION

The proposed solar-powered dual-temperature bag operates through a systematic integration of renewable energy harvesting, embedded control, and thermoelectric regulation. The process begins with the solar panel (18.15 V, 5.66 A, 100 W), which converts sunlight into electrical energy. This energy is directed to a charge controller (30 A, 24 V), which stabilizes the voltage and current before supplying it to the rechargeable battery (3.7 V, 2.2 Ah, 100 Wh). The charge controller ensures safe operation by preventing overcharging and deep discharging, thereby extending battery life. The stored energy in the battery allows the system to function reliably even in the absence of sunlight, making it suitable for portable use. The Arduino Uno serves as the central processing unit, coordinating sensor inputs, user commands, and actuator responses. A thermistor sensor placed inside the compartment continuously measures the internal temperature. These readings are processed by the Arduino, which compares them against preset threshold values. Based on this comparison, the Arduino controls a relay module that switches the Peltier device on or off. The Peltier module, consuming between 112 W and 288 W depending on load conditions, provides either heating or cooling depending on the selected mode. User interaction is facilitated through a DPDT switch, which allows manual selection between heating and cooling modes. In heating mode, the Peltier module generates heat on one side of the compartment, while in cooling mode, it produces cold on the opposite side. For additional flexibility, a manual toggle switch enables direct user

control, allowing the system to be turned on or off or specific functions to be activated without relying solely on automatic regulation.

Figure 3: Block Diagram of the Proposed Work

Figure 4: Hardware Connection

3.1. Solar Panel:

The solar panel is the main source of power for the system. It converts sunlight into electrical energy using photovoltaic cells. With a rating of 18.15 V, 5.56 A and 100 W, it generates sufficient DC power to operate the system during daylight hours. The produced energy is supplied to the charge controller, making the system independent of conventional power sources and environmentally friendly.

Solar Pannel Power:

Given ,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Voltage} &= 18.15 \text{ V} \\ \text{Current} &= 5.56 \text{ A} \\ \text{Power} &= VI = 18.15 * 5.56 = 100W \end{aligned}$$

Figure 5: I-V and P-V Characteristics of a Solar Cell

Source: Adapted from [8]

3.2. Charge Controller:

The charge controller regulates the electrical power coming from the solar panel. It ensures that the battery is charged safely by preventing overcharging and deep discharge. Rated at 30 A and 24 V, it also provides a stable and regulated output to the load. This component plays a crucial role in improving battery life and protecting the overall system.

3.3. Battery:

The battery stores the electrical energy generated by the solar panel for later use. With a rating of 3.7 V and 2.2 Ah (approximately 100 Wh) it supplies power to the system during low sunlight or nighttime conditions. The battery ensures uninterrupted operation of the Peltier module and control electronics, improving system reliability.

Each Battery: 3.7 V, 2.2 Ah

Configuration: 3S4P

*Battery Voltage $V = 3 * 3.7 = 11.1V$ (Series connection)*

*Battery Capacity $Ah = 4 * 2.2 = 8.8Ah$*

Battery Energy

- $E = 11.1 * 8.8$
- $E = 97.68Wh$

Thus these calculations shows the battery energy which is upto 100Wh then we can calculate the Battery Backup Time

- *If the peltier consumes 288W ,*
 $Then t = 97.68 / 288$
 $t = 0.339 hr \sim 20 mins$
- *If peltier consumes 112W*
 $Then t = 97.68 / 112 = 0.87 hr \sim 52 mins$

3.4. DPDT switch:

The DPDT switch is used to control how power flows to the load. It allows the user to manually switch between different operating modes, such as changing the direction or type of operation. This makes the system more flexible to use and also improves safety, because the load can be easily isolated or turned off whenever needed

3.5. Peltier Module (Load):

The Peltier module is the main load of the system and is responsible for cooling. It operates based on the thermoelectric effect, where heat is transferred from one side to another when DC current is applied. The power consumption ranges from 72 W to 288 W, depending on operating conditions. This module is commonly used in refrigeration and temperature control applications.

Figure 8: Schematic Diagram of a Thermoelectric Peltier Module
Source: Adapted from [13]

Figure 9: Construction of Peltier
Source: Adapted from [13]

Peltier can deliver max voltage of around 12 V and min voltage of 6 V with current of 6A then the power can be calculated as

Peltier power , $P=VI$

Example consider the peltier consumes 12V and 6A then power would be ,

$$P = 12 * 6 = 72 W$$

3.6. Temperature Sensor (Thermistor):

The temperature sensor continuously monitors the temperature of the Peltier module or its surroundings. A thermistor changes its resistance with temperature variation and provides real-time temperature data to the Arduino. This helps in maintaining the desired temperature and protects the system from overheating.

3.7. Arduino (Microcontroller Unit):

The Arduino works as the main controller of the system. It continuously reads the temperature using a thermistor and understands how hot or cold it is inside. Based on this information, the Arduino decides when the Peltier module should be turned ON or OFF. It automatically controls the relay according to the preset temperature limits, making sure the system works smartly, safely, and uses energy efficiently.

3.8. Relay:

The relay functions as an electrically operated switch controlled by the Arduino. It allows the low-power control signals from the Arduino to safely switch the high-power Peltier load. The relay also provides electrical isolation between the control circuit and the power circuit, ensuring safe operation.

3.9. Toggle Switch:

The toggle switch provides manual control over the relay operation. It allows the user to override automatic control for testing, maintenance, or emergency shutdown. This feature enhances user interaction and system safety.

3.10. Power Supply Unit:

The power supply unit provides regulated DC power to the Arduino, sensors, and relay circuitry. It ensures stable voltage levels for reliable system operation. The supply can be derived from the battery or an external regulated source, making the system flexible and dependable.

Table 1 : System Specification Table

Component	Specification
Solar Panel	100 W
Battery	11.1 V, 8.8 Ah
Peltier chip	TEC1-12706
Heat Sink	Aluminium
Thermistor	10 kΩ NTC
Charge Controller	30 A PWM
Cooling Range	28°C → 19.6°C
Heating Range	28°C → 47°C

3.11. System Flow Summary:

- The solar panel converts sunlight into electrical energy.
- The charge controller regulates this power and safely charges the battery.
- The battery stores energy and supplies power when sunlight is low or unavailable.
- The power supply unit provides regulated DC power to the Arduino and control circuits.
- The temperature sensor (thermistor) continuously measures temperature.
- The Arduino reads the temperature and compares it with preset limits.
- If cooling is required, the Arduino activates the relay.
- The relay switches the Peltier module ON or OFF to control cooling.
- The toggle switch allows manual override for testing or emergency use.
- The system works continuously to maintain the required temperature using solar power.

Table 2 : Mathematical Models Used in the Proposed System

Sl no	Parameter	Equation	Purpose
1	Solar Panel Power	$P=VI$	Calculates the electrical power generated by the solar panel.
2	Battery Energy	$E = V * Ah$	Determines the total energy stored in the battery.
3	Fourier's Law of Heat Conduction	$q=-kA*(d/dT)$	Describes heat transfer through the metal enclosure.
4	Joule Heating	$P=I^2R$	Calculates resistive heat losses in electrical components.
5	Seebeck Voltage	$V=\alpha\Delta T$	Represents the thermoelectric voltage generated due to a temperature difference.
6	Battery Efficiency	$\eta=(E_{in}/E_{out}) \times 100\%$	Determines battery energy conversion efficiency.
7	Heat Transfer	$Q=mc\Delta T$	Calculates the amount of heat absorbed or released by the stored contents during the heating or cooling process.

4. TESTING RESULTS

To evaluate the thermal performance of the Peltier-based system, temperature was recorded every five minutes using an Arduino with a digital sensor. The readings, displayed on the serial monitor, tracked the rate of temperature rise and fall in heating and cooling modes. Observations for both modes are shown in the table below.

Table 3 : Temperature VS Time Experimental Reading Table

Time (min)	Cooling Temperature (°C)	Heating Temperature (°C)
0	28.0	28.0
5	26.0	30.0
10	24.2	36.0
15	23.1	39.0
20	21.9	42.0
25	20.0	45.0
30	19.6	47.0

Figure 10 : Graphical representation of the tested result

The Temperature vs Time graph shows the Peltier module's thermal response over 30 minutes. Starting at 28°C, cooling mode lowers the temperature to 19.6°C steadily, while heating mode raises it to 47°C, with rapid heating in the first 10 minutes. The graph demonstrates the module's effective and predictable dual functionality in both heating and cooling.

4.1. Advantages:

The proposed solar-powered portable dual-temperature box offers several advantages over conventional insulated storage systems. The key advantages are:

- **Dual-Mode Operation:** The system provides both heating and cooling using a single Peltier module by simply reversing the polarity through a DPDT switch.
- **Portable Design:** The compact size and rechargeable lithium-ion battery make the system suitable for transportation and outdoor applications.
- **Renewable Energy Powered:** The battery can be recharged using a solar panel, reducing dependence on conventional electrical power and promoting sustainable operation.
- **Low Power Consumption:** The thermoelectric cooling system consumes relatively less power compared to conventional compressor-based refrigeration systems for small-scale portable applications.
- **Environmentally Friendly:** The Peltier module operates without refrigerants, eliminating harmful emissions associated with traditional cooling systems.
- **Simple Construction:** The proposed design consists of readily available electronic components, making it economical, easy to assemble, and simple to maintain.
- **Wide Range of Applications:** The system can be used for transporting food, beverages, medicines, vaccines, cosmetics, and other temperature-sensitive products.

4.2. limitations:

Although the proposed system performs effectively for portable heating and cooling applications, it has several limitations:

- The heating and cooling modes are selected manually using a DPDT switch and do not operate automatically.
- The system continuously heats or cools until the user manually switches it off, as automatic temperature regulation is not implemented.
- The cooling performance of the Peltier module is lower than that of conventional vapor-compression refrigeration systems.
- The battery backup time is limited by the battery capacity and the power consumption of the Peltier module.
- The charging efficiency depends on the availability of sunlight and environmental conditions.
- Heat dissipation efficiency is influenced by the heat sink and cooling fan performance, which directly affect the overall system efficiency.

4.3. Future Scope:

The proposed system provides a foundation for further improvements that can enhance its performance and usability. Future work may include:

- **Automatic Temperature Control:** Implement relay-based ON/OFF control or PID-based temperature regulation to maintain a user-defined temperature automatically.
- **IoT-Based Monitoring:** Integrate Wi-Fi-enabled controllers such as the ESP32 for remote temperature monitoring through a mobile application.
- **Battery Management System (BMS):** Incorporate a BMS to monitor battery voltage, current, State of Charge (SoC), and ensure safe charging and discharging.
- **Improved Thermal Insulation:** Use advanced insulation materials to reduce heat loss and improve energy efficiency.
- **Data Logging:** Store temperature and battery data on an SD card or cloud platform for performance analysis.
- **Intelligent Control:** Integrate machine learning or AI algorithms to optimize power consumption and temperature regulation based on operating conditions.

5. CONCLUSION

The proposed dual-temperature bag is designed to provide a reliable and convenient solution for transporting temperature-sensitive items such as food, beverages, medicines, and biological samples. Maintaining a controlled temperature during travel is often challenging, especially in the absence of continuous power supply. This system addresses the problem by integrating thermoelectric technology, intelligent control, and renewable energy sources into a compact and portable design. At the core of the system is a Peltier module, which operates on the thermoelectric effect and can function in both heating and cooling modes. By reversing the direction of current flow, the same module can either absorb heat or release heat, allowing flexible temperature control based on user requirements. A metal box placed inside the bag ensures uniform temperature distribution by improving thermal conduction, thereby preventing localized hot or cold spots and protecting the stored items.

An Arduino microcontroller acts as the central control unit of the system. It continuously monitors the internal temperature of the bag using a temperature sensor and processes the data in real time. Based on predefined temperature thresholds, the Arduino controls a relay module that switches the Peltier module ON or OFF. If the temperature exceeds safe limits, the system automatically cuts off power to prevent overheating or excessive

cooling. This automatic protection mechanism ensures safe and reliable operation without requiring constant user supervision. The system is powered by a rechargeable battery, which makes it suitable for portable use. To enhance sustainability and off-grid usability, the battery can also be charged using a solar panel, making the design environmentally friendly and energy efficient. A DPDT switch is provided to allow the user to easily select between heating and cooling modes, giving full control over the operating condition of the bag. Additionally, a toggle switch enables manual override during testing, maintenance, or emergency situations.

A 16×2 LCD display is integrated into the system to provide real-time temperature information. This allows users to continuously monitor the internal conditions of the bag and ensures transparency in system operation. The display improves user interaction and makes the system easy to operate even for non-technical users.

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